

Synthesis of Some Substituted Hydroxytriazenes

S. M. Dugar and N. C. Sogani

In connection with study of the effect of substituents on the pK_a values and the stabilities of the resulting metal chelates, eleven hydroxytriazenes (Table I) have been prepared and some of their physical properties studied. Successful use of hydroxytriazenes as effective chelating agents has already been reported¹⁻³.

TABLE I

Hydroxytriazene	Cryst. from	M.P.	Colour.	Crystal shape.	%Carbon.	%H.	%N.	%Cl.	
R.	R'. R''.	EtOH.							
Me	OMe H	60%	101.6°	White	Needles	Found: 52.00 Reqd.: 53.03	5.96 6.12	23.31 23.10	..
..	Cl H	80	141.45°	Light buff	..	Found: 45.15 Reqd.: 45.20	4.38 4.28	22.73 22.64	19.32 19.10
..	H Cl	80	81.5°	Cream-yellow	..	Found: 45.10 Reqd.: 45.20	4.10 4.34	22.86 22.64	19.23 19.10
Et	H H	20	44.5°	White	..	Found: 68.12 Reqd.: 68.64	6.69 6.71	26.01 25.44	..
..	Me H	20	78°	..	..	Found: 60.14 Reqd.: 60.31	7.42 7.31	23.37 23.44	..
..	OMe H	20	73°	Shining white	Plates	Found: 55.49 Reqd.: 55.97	5.50 6.71	21.72 21.52	..
..	Cl H	80	102°	Pale yellow	Needles	Found: 48.25 Reqd.: 48.13	4.83 5.05	20.87 21.05	17.91 17.78
..	H Cl	Distilled under reduced pressure	131-32°/0.3 mm	Yellow	Syrupy liquid	Found: 45.18 Reqd.: 45.20	4.10 4.34	22.65 22.65	19.30 19.10
Pr	H H	20%	61°	White	Needles	Found: 59.92 Reqd.: 60.31	7.62 7.31	23.58 23.44	..
..	Me H	20	44°	..	..	Found: 62.20 Reqd.: 62.15	7.50 7.62	21.63 21.74	..
..	Cl H	40	81.5°	Pale yellow	..	Found: 60.38 Reqd.: 60.59	5.49 5.08	19.88 19.67	16.43 16.59

1. Sogani and Bhattacharyya, *this Journal*, 1959, **36**, 503.

2. Sogani *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 531.

3. Gupta and Sogani, *ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 771.

General Method of Preparation.—An aqueous solution of freshly prepared alkyl hydroxylamine was stirred mechanically with sufficient quantity of crushed ice to keep the temperature at 0° and then kept in an ice bath. A solution of molar benzenediazonium chloride was then added slowly to the above solution (under mechanical stirring). A concentrated solution of sodium acetate was added portionwise occasionally to maintain the pH at about 5. The required hydroxytriazenes were generally thrown down in the form of a granular precipitate excepting 3-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-*o*-chlorophenyltriazene which settled down as a viscous oily liquid. The solids were filtered under suction and crystallised from EtOH-H₂O mixtures.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF RAJASTHAN,
JAIPUR.

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